

THE URGENCE OF CULTURAL INVESTMENT AND THE APPLICATION OF DIGITAL LITERATURE TO THE COMMUNITY

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Abstract

Digital literacy is the interests, attitudes and abilities of individuals who directly use digital technology and communication tools to access, manage, integrate, analyze and evaluate information, build new knowledge, create and communicate with others in order to participate effectively in society. The implementation of education is held as a process of civilizing and empowering students that lasts a lifetime. This principle is in accordance with the general provisions of the 2003 National Education System Law Article 1 paragraph 1 which states that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control

Keywords: Culture, Literacy, Digital

A. Introduction

Today, various educational institutions ranging from primary education to higher education have built information literacy programs. Information literacy which is a translation of information literacy in a concise sense is defined as information literacy or information literacy. Mastery of information literacy is seen as very important in the learning process so that it becomes part of an educational program. In a broader scope, that the information literacy program is actually a community empowerment program, especially in the information field¹.

Literacy is a positive activity that is useful for adding insight, mindset and expanding knowledge. Literacy culture is often echoed by people in various countries. Even if we look at the ancient Greeks, they all highly value literacy and philosophy. Even at the time of the Prophet Muhammad SAW, the first verse came down to teach humans how influential literacy culture is.

In any era, literacy culture seems to be at the forefront in opening the gates of broader education. The urgency of literacy seems to have become part of the nation's future. This is because the government is not able to strengthen the literacy culture in the dynamics of community development.

Robinson stated that literacy is the ability to read and write sufficiently to compete economically entirely. He further explained that literacy is the ability to read and write that is related to one's success in the academic community so that literacy is a tool that is owned to be able to achieve success in the social environment.

Information technology is one thing that cannot be separated from human life. Because this information technology has existed since centuries ago and is still growing. Without information technology, humans will find it challenging to communicate and convey information. Now information technology is developing so fast.

¹Herlina. Library and Information Science. Palembang: IAIN Raden Fatah Press. 2006

Lately the development of technology is very rapid, for example, games, music, videos, cellphones, internet, etc. Many people are addicted to social media that lulls its users. Especially among teenagers such as students and college students. At an age that is vulnerable and easily influenced by new things, there is a lot of ineffective and efficient use of technology.

Along with the technological revolution, there are many impacts that occur on the pattern of human life, both in terms of positive and negative. The effect that is so visible today is the decline in one's level of literature and the level of one's willingness to write down every thought and result of his work in a manuscript which is either in electronic form or in written form on paper or even stones and trees. Starting to decline groups who fight for and learn the teachings of the previous people through books or writings and rewrite them. There is no longer the spirit of Plato, Socrates, Ibn Sina and the like in fighting for a literacy culture.²

B. Formulation Of The Problem

1. How to build a literacy culture among students and college students?
2. What is the role and function of digital literacy in education?
3. What is the relationship between technological developments and literacy culture?
4. What are the opportunities and challenges of digital literacy?

C. Building A Literature Culture

Literacy culture is a culture in society that includes all human efforts related to reading and writing activities. The main components in the formation of a literacy culture are reading, writing and critical thinking activities. The purpose of literacy culture is to create a tradition of thinking that is followed by the process of reading and writing so that it can produce helpful scientific writings³.

The earliest literacy culture to develop is in individual children who are formed through the reading and writing tradition given by the family. In creating a literacy culture in society, the family is the smallest unit that equips children with literacy skills at home. Literacy culture by the family is formed in children in a fun way. Children's interest in reading and

²Dea Julia Ningsih Seregar,
http://perlibatandeaajulia.weebly.com/uploads/1/.../makalh_literasi_median_n_digital.pdf accessed July 15, 2017

³Muslim. *Fostering Literacy Culture and Reading Interest from the Village* (PDF). Gorontalo: Ideas Publishing, 2017.

writing activities is carried out with literacy activities at home by all family members. The results of children's literacy culture include the ability to think critically, communicate and the emergence of creativity and collaboration in solving problems. In addition, literacy culture can also produce individual characters and the emergence of empathy in children⁴.

The development of a literacy culture in the home can be done by placing various kinds of reading in a particular place that is easy to find and reach by children. Reading material can be provided in the form of books, magazines, or newspapers. While writing activities are supported by the provision of stationery at home. Reading material can be stored in a cupboard, drawer or bookshelf. A large house can also be made into a reading corner or family library as a place for cultural literacy development activities⁵.

As previously stated, literacy can be defined as the ability to read and write which we know as literacy or literacy. But now literacy has a broad meaning, so literacy is no longer a single meaning but contains multiple substances (multi literacies). There are various kinds of literacy or literacy, for example computer literacy (computer literacy), media literacy (media literacy), technological literacy (technology literacy), economic literacy (economic literacy), information literacy (information literacy), and even moral literacy (moral literacy). . So, literacy or literacy can be interpreted as technology literacy, information literacy, critical thinking, sensitive to the environment, and even liable to politics. A person is said to be literate if he is able to understand something because he reads the correct information and does something based on his understanding of the contents of the reading. Sensitivity or literacy in someone certainly does not just appear. No human is literate since birth. Creating a literate generation requires a long process and conducive means. This process starts from childhood and from the family environment, then is supported or developed in schools, social circles, and work environments. Literacy culture is also closely related to learning patterns in schools and the availability of reading materials in libraries. But we also realize that literacy does not have to be obtained from school or higher education. High academic ability does not guarantee someone will be literate.

According to Kimbey, a habit is an act that is done repeatedly without any element of coercion. Habits are not something that is natural in humans but are the result of the learning

⁴Setiawan, Rosie. GLS Manual Series: Fostering a Literacy Culture at Home (PDF). Jakarta: Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education, Ministry of Education and Culture. 2019.

⁵Ibid

process and the influence of experience and the state of the surrounding environment. Therefore, habits can be nurtured and developed⁶. While reading is a process of communicating ideas between the author and the reader, where in this process the reader tries to interpret the meaning of the symbols or the author's language to capture and understand the author's ideas.⁷ So the habit of reading is a reading activity that is carried out repeatedly without any element of coercion. Reading habits include time to read, types of reading materials, how to get reading materials, and the number of books/reading materials read. The ability to read is the basis for the creation of reading habits. However, the ability to read in a person is not a guarantee for the result of reading habits because reading habits are also influenced by other factors such as the availability of reading materials. The development of the practice of doing activities is a learning process that is affected by internal and external factors⁸.

From the facts that we have seen about learning Indonesian above, the direction of learning must be changed. Indonesian language learning is directed at efforts to build a literacy culture, especially knowing that can increase students' activities using teaching materials in life. Students learn language or literature for the real world, not the world of school. Di Yanni stated that literacy-based learning is done by developing ideas or ideas through developing questions at the time of writing, then setting them through the connection between ideas and the controversy of each statement.⁹ Literacy culture-based learning in education has advantages because the literacy model is not only intended so that students have the capacity to understand the conceptual meaning of discourse but the ability to participate fully actively in applying social and intellectual understanding.¹⁰

Literacy culture-based learning will condition students to become literate. Improving literacy skills in education is in line with educational goals, namely the development of the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. . Obtaining this goal can be done by students if they

⁶Gregory A Kimbley. Habits. Encyclopedia Americana, 1975. p.13.

⁷Wijono. Reading Guidance. School Library News, p. 40.

⁸Yunus Winoto. How to Know Your Reading Ability. Reader Guide. 1994. h. 151.

⁹Di Yanni, Robert and Pat C. Hoy. The Scriber Handbook for Writing. Boston: Allya & Bacon. 1995.

¹⁰Baynham, Mike. Literacy Practices: Investigating Literacy in Social Contexts. London: Longman. 1995.

have become literate figures. The students have the provision of literacy in themselves so that they are able to equip themselves with the expected abilities.

The process of developing language and literary skills is carried out by developing cognitive abilities, analysis, synthesis, evaluation, and creation through a direct study of social conditions by using the ability to think carefully and critically. The process of understanding students' social phenomena with straightforward introduction will make it easier for students to develop their competencies. Students must be familiar with reading various information and accessing information from electronic media and written media. In addition, he needs to follow the development of civilization that is happening factually. Therefore, in developing literacy-based language and literary competence, it is necessary to support the availability of facilities in building literate people.

The literacy process contains four universal characteristics, namely:

- textual purpose; there is a written communication message that fits its purpose
- Agreement, the meaning of the message is interpreted as intended
- Good use of language (as in poetry); to clarify the message must use his language skills
- The risk taken is to accept new challenges in language¹¹.

Based on data from the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbud) literacy activities are influenced by several factors, namely Skills, Access, Alternatives and culture. Based on data from the Ministry of Education and Culture, the Alibaca Index shows that only nine provinces are in the medium category, 24 provinces are in the low category, and one province is in the deficient category. The average national Alibaca index is at the point of 37.32% which is relatively low¹².

Education in the current information age can be formulated as a human development effort which is characterized by increased knowledge, skills, abilities, and behavior of individuals and groups in which the person is located, through continuous learning activities.¹³

¹¹ <https://kuninganmass.com/kultur-literasi-era-digital/accessed> on 7 June 2022

¹² databoks.katadata.co.id

¹³ Yusufhadi Miarso, *Matching the Seeds of Education*, (Jakarta: Kencana, 2004), p. 403

The activities of educators in the classroom when carrying out literacy-based Indonesian language learning are lighter, namely:

- Directing student activities
- Selecting and preparing learning materials
- Checking the work of students
- Leading the scientific communication system
- Coordinate in preparing the classroom setting for literacy activities.

D. The Role And Function Of Digital Literature

According to Gilster, the concept of digital literacy is defined as the ability to understand and use information from various digital sources, in other words the ability to read, write, and relate to information using technology and formats that existed at the time.¹⁴

Digital literacy is the interests, attitudes and abilities of individuals who directly use digital technology and communication tools to access, manage, integrate, analyze and evaluate information, build new knowledge, create and communicate with others in order to participate effectively in society.¹⁵

The term digital literacy became popular around 2005. Digital literacy means the ability to relate to hypertextual information in the sense of computer-aided unordered reading.¹⁶

The term digital literacy was used in the 1980s, generally meaning the ability to relate to hypertextual information in the sense of computer-aided non-sequential or non-sequential reading.¹⁷

Other authors use the term digital literacy to denote a broad concept that links together various competency-based literacy and communication technology skills, but emphasizes the ability to evaluate more “soft” information and link knowledge together understanding and attitudes.¹⁸

¹⁴P.Gilster, P. Digital literacy. New York; Wiley. 1997.

¹⁵Jazimatul Husna, et al, Digital Literacy Anthology, (Yogyakarta: Azyan Mitra Media, 2017), 153

¹⁶ Davis, Charles H.; Shaw, Deborah (eds). Introduction to information science and technology. Medford, NJ: Information Today. 2011.

¹⁷Ibid

¹⁸Op.Cit

Digital literacy is also defined as a set of attitudes, understandings, and skills to handle and communicate information and knowledge effectively in various media and formats. There are definitions that include the terms connecting, communicating; those with a record management or records management perspective use the words deleting and preserving. Sometimes the term finding is broken down into source selection, retrieval and accessing.¹⁹ Although digital literacy is important in an age where information is in digital form, it should not be forgotten that another important part of digital literacy is knowing when to use non-digital sources.

According to Bawden (2008), the digital literacy component consists of four parts as follows:

1. Supporting milestones are literacy itself and computer literacy, information and communication technology
2. Background knowledge is divided into the world of information and the nature of information resources
3. Competencies in the form of:
 - ❖ understanding of digital and non-digital formats
 - ❖ creation and communication of digital information
 - ❖ information evaluation
 - ❖ knowledge assembly
 - ❖ information literacy
 - ❖ media literacy
4. Attitudes and perspectives are the things that create a link between the new concept of digital literacy and the old idea of literacy. Individuals do not have enough skills and competencies but they must be based on a moral framework, which is associated with an educated person. Of all the components of digital literacy, perhaps the most difficult to teach is the moral framework, but it is most closely related to the term information²⁰

Since the opening of freedom of information and media technology, the growth of mass media and new media has increased significantly. Communication media that has

¹⁹ Martin, A. Digital literacy and the “digital society”. In C. Lanskhear & M. Konel(eds). Digital literacy: concepts, policies, and paradoxes. New York: Peter Lang, 2008.

²⁰Ibid

metamorphosed into digital media are increasingly diverse in development, more easily represented by the growth of smartphones and the like. Nowadays, the penetration of various types of media has penetrated into various circles and communities in society, regardless of social and economic strata. The use of smartphone communication media and the like has shifted to a certain people's lifestyle. In this context, it can be analogized that media technology has taken part in certain roles in society. Along with the development of communication technology of course there are several consequences, both positive and negative connotations of the influence of the use of communication media technology. According to Baran, the media influence the culture of the audience in various ways. So do not be surprised if the life of our society today cannot be separated by the presence of communication media technology²¹.

The pressure is getting more intense when “the media are competing with each other” in providing information services to their consumers. The high penetration of communication media makes it more difficult to control the impact. Now consumers do not just get information, knowledge, and entertainment, but can interact directly. At the same time, the media instills new ideological values in the form of lifestyle, consumer culture and models of imitating the attitudes and behavior of certain artists/actors popularized by the media. Therefore, it is time for media penetration that is increasingly vigorous and free to be balanced with media literacy as a culture of counteracting the negative impact of media. Besides that, media literacy also aims to protect consumers who are vulnerable and weak against the impact of media penetration of new media culture²².

It could be that the progress of media literacy is based on the increasingly rapid onslaught of media information that is not balanced with the ability to consume it. So we need a new culture in consuming media in a healthy manner. Along with the development of information and communication technology, media literacy also applies to consumers of on-line media, or new media that are spread through internet networks. Media literacy certainly cannot run well without the participation of the community. The role can be in the form of individuals, communities, groups, and local local cultures. The role of the individual is more focused on the guidance of parents as the head of the family on media consumption in their

²¹ Stanley J. Baran, Dennis K. Davis. *Mass Communication Theory: Foundations, Upheavals, and the Future*. Salemba Humanika: 2010. h. 23.

²²Journal. <https://binus.ac.id/malang/2017/09/pentingnya-literasi-media-di-dunia/>

environment. Likewise, supervision in the community, certain community groups who are concerned about the development of media convergence,

One way to increase awareness of media literacy is through family communication, because family is the smallest unit of socialization. This role will mainly be taken by housewives. Educating rural housewives to be "literate" media is important to do to open their horizons about the community's right to media, forms of literacy, and the function of media for social life. However, to achieve this, housewives need to be assisted in literacy on TV shows because they need to increase their understanding of people's rights to TV shows.

E. Relationship Between Technology Development And Literature Culture

Advances in technology today can not be separated from human life. Various information that occurs in various parts of the world can now be directly known to us thanks to technological advances (globalization). Now the world is getting smaller and smaller. One can easily access information both at home and abroad.

Of course, these technological advances have caused such great changes in human life with all its civilizations and cultures.

Technological changes also have a huge impact on the transformation of values in society, both in positive and negative terms. Especially among teenagers, such as students and college students. Currently, in Indonesia, we can see the great influence of technological advances on the behavior of the younger generation. Technological advances such as television, telephones and mobile phones (HP), and even the internet have not only hit teenagers who live in cities, but have also been enjoyed by teenagers in remote villages. Not to mention the rise of social media that lulls its users.

Of course, this also has an impact on the decline in one's level of literature and the level of one's willingness to write down every thought and result of his work in a manuscript, either in electronic form or in written form on paper. Today's youth have been busy with a series of activities in cyberspace. In fact, they are the potential successors of the great people who have initiated the inventions of sophisticated technology.

Literacy is starting to disappear, and will continue to disappear if as the next generation a student does not care about this culture anymore. It is undeniable that children are easily too

lazy to study and rewrite them according to the results of new studies, students in this globalization era prefer to study the results of other people's studies without rewriting them to preserve them. The impact is that there is no continuation of the studies to be studied, all books become obsolete without anyone updating – for now there are still those who care – because the literacy culture is starting to fade among intellectuals and among students as social control.

The existence of technology that is constantly undergoing changes should be a positive impetus in efforts to improve literacy culture. A person can easily express his ideas and ideas easily. For example, making research articles or scientific papers that he can write through blogger. Thus knowledge can continue to be explored by blog readers.

Basically writing is not a boring thing, it just takes patience to finish it. When someone is writing a scientific paper, then he needs reliable sources to support his writing. These sources can be obtained by reading several references which can also be accessed easily via the internet. If used properly, the technological revolution will also have a positive influence on literacy culture.

Education and literacy skills are two very important things in our lives. The progress of a country directly depends on the literacy rate in that country. Educated people are expected to do their job well. Historically, according to Prof. Dr. Tarwotjo M.Sc as quoted by Asul Wiyanto in the introduction to his book entitled “Skilled in Writing Paragraphs”, the product of Literacy activities in the form of writing, is an intellectual heritage that we will not find in prehistoric times. In other words, if there is no writing, it's the same as we are in prehistoric times. Writing is a form of historical recording that can be passed down from generation to generation, even for centuries.

In the history of Islamic civilization, we can see how the Islamic Literacy tradition gave birth to the writings of classical Islamic thinkers and scholars who are hundreds of years old and still exist to be studied in various Islamic educational institutions, especially Islamic boarding schools. The books written by Muslim scholars and intellectuals of the classical era are a very valuable intellectual heritage for the development of Islamic intellectual treasures from generation to generation.

Writing is evidence of the historical track record of human civilization in the form of events, experiences, knowledge, thoughts, and science. Writing can penetrate and trace the halls of space and time in the past. If only in this era there were no written songs or people who wanted to write, surely we would return to pre-historic times. But in fact, our current civilization can be said to be a writing civilization or a text civilization. It is evident from the flood of information that we receive every day from various media, both print and electronic, mostly in the form of text or writing. In short, writing has filled the entire space of modern human life in this era of globalization.

There are several programs that are feasible for the success of literacy activities. First, we need to improve the quality and equity of education in order to promote higher literacy rates. Infrastructure (facilities) and superstructure (human resources) need to be developed to reach all corners of the country. Don't let people in the interior of the archipelago still find it difficult to learn because there are no schools, lack of teachers, or lack of other facilities. The state is responsible for providing educational facilities for its citizens. Second, we build more libraries in all areas as comfortable places to read, large collections of books, and offering interesting activities. Third, ongoing programs are needed to introduce more books and encourage interest in reading books to schools and the general public. Don't get hung up on the ceremony, but focus on breakthroughs that are more grounded and entice young people to read. Fourth, from the publisher's perspective, we encourage more books to be published, especially quality books from various fields. The more offers of interesting books, the more alternative reading for the community. Fifth, we support the power of civil society to work together with the government and all parties to build a civilization of reading books. This can take the form of establishing reading parks throughout the archipelago, programs to encourage reading, or other steps that may be taken to provoke young people to love books. especially quality books from various fields. The more offers of interesting books, the more alternative reading for the community. Fifth, we support the power of civil society to work together with the government and all parties to build a civilization of reading books. This can take the form of establishing reading parks throughout the archipelago, programs to encourage reading, or other steps that may be taken to provoke young people to love books. especially quality books from various fields. The more offers of interesting books, the more alternative reading for the community. Fifth, we support the power of civil society to work together with the government and all parties to build a civilization of reading books. This can

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F. Digital Literature Challenges And Opportunities

Quoted from the Digital Literacy Support Materials of the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture, a digital literacy researcher named Douglas AJ Belshaw stated in his thesis that there are eight essential elements to develop digital literacy, including:

1. Cultural, namely understanding the various contexts of users of the digital world
2. Cognitive, namely the power of thinking in assessing content
3. Constructive, namely the creation of something that is expert and actual
4. Communicative, namely understanding the performance of networks and communications in the digital world
5. Responsible self-confidence
6. Creative, doing new things in new ways
7. Critical in dealing with content
8. Socially responsible²³

The development of digital equipment and access to digital information is flooding, skills in digital literacy are things that must be mastered by internet users. It was recorded through research published by wearesocial.sg that in 2017 there were 132 million internet users in Indonesia with a growth rate of 51% in just a year.

²³ Digital Literacy Support Materials Ministry of Education and Culture RI

As one of the countries with the largest number of internet users in the world, the development of the digital world in Indonesia has two opposite sides in relation to the development of digital literacy.

On the one hand, easy access to information makes it easier for us to fulfill our needs and curiosity, on the other hand, by not having skills in the digital world, this will have a negative impact on our lives.

The development of digital equipment and access to information is certainly a challenge as well as an opportunity. With internet usage that is relatively high, the Indonesian government must think about the best way to deal with hoax news or information, hate speech, and intolerant behavior that can be easily found on social media.

Digital media allows for opportunities, such as increased profits in the e-commerce business, the birth of new digital media-based jobs, and the development of literacy skills without negating print-based text.

The government sees this as an opportunity to create 1,000 technopreneurs with a business value of \$10 billion with an e-commerce value reaching \$130 billion or equivalent to Rp1,800 trillion by 2020.

With the internet network as well, digitization can be used as an intermediary medium to get to literacy practices that can produce print-based texts. For example, writing activities on a personal blog can be directed to collect writings which can then be printed into a book containing a collection of writings with certain themes taken from personal blogs.²⁴

Therefore, it is appropriate for youth, especially students, to apply the importance of literacy culture to the surrounding environment. This is because the literacy culture does not die. The public must also get used to reading so as not to easily fall into false information that can damage harmony between each other.

As a nation that has abundant natural resources, it is fitting for the Indonesian people to be able to rise from this adversity. The lack of literacy culture is one of the main factors in the decline of the Indonesian nation. Indonesian youth also have to look at other countries, this is

²⁴Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture Literacy Movement

to increase their enthusiasm to be able to compete in the international arena by making Indonesia proud.

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